

To regulate or not to regulate: The destination management dilemma in handling the intensity of tourism

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ABSTRACT

Excessive tourism pressure signals unsustainable destination tourism. This study investigates the relationship between regulatory pressure and tourism intensity in Florence, Italy, a UNESCO World Heritage Site. Although tourism has generated economic benefits, it has also raised concerns about resource exploitation and environmental degradation, prompting local policy interventions. Using a mixed-methods approach, we explore whether regulatory measures influence tourism intensity. Results indicate that tourism-centered regulations increased over time, suggesting that policymakers resort to regulation as a tool to manage growing tourism intensity. Additionally, we found a negative association between regulatory pressure and tourism intensity, particularly when policies are explicitly aimed at tourism. These effects remain robust across different measures of tourism intensity. Notably, tourism intensity is unaffected by city tax levels but is positively associated with inflation and hospitality rates. The study advances sustainable destination management research by highlighting the regulatory tools most effective for mitigating overtourism, offering actionable insights for policymakers seeking to preserve cultural heritage while managing tourism development.

1. Introduction

In response to tourism's negative externalities, researchers and policymakers have increasingly turned to sustainable tourism as a framework for reconciling economic development with environmental and sociocultural integrity (Iversen et al., 2024). In this perspective, sustainable tourism aims to limit resource depletion and environmental degradation, while protecting residents' quality of life (Baños-Pino et al., 2024; Iversen et al., 2024; Kirilenko et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022). Prior research has predominantly focused on constructing indicator-based metrics to assess unsustainable tourism (Marinello et al., 2023; Page & Duignan, 2023). These measures help policymakers track tourism pressure compared to carrying-capacity thresholds (Ferrante et al., 2018; Ivars-Baidal et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2023) and have been applied to examine impacts in national parks (Randle & Hoye, 2016), rural destinations (Iversen et al., 2024; Yamagishi & Doering, 2025), and protected areas more broadly (Badola et al., 2018). However, despite their utility for *ex post* diagnosis, such indicators rarely translate into operational levers that can actively regulate tourism intensity or mitigate its negative impacts.

In light of these limitations, local governments have increasingly

deployed regulatory instruments to move from monitoring toward more active, governance-based destination management (Tokarchuk et al., 2021). This evolution has intensified scholarly and policy interest in regulation as a means to tackle the underlying drivers of overtourism and to manage the trade-offs between sustainability objectives and economic development (Iversen et al., 2024; Nepal et al., 2019). Therefore, this study investigates the effectiveness of regulatory interventions in managing tourism pressure.

Within this regulatory turn, fiscal and planning instruments have emerged as two central policy levers. Tourist taxes, for instance, are typically conceived to generate revenues for public spending (Anguera-Torrell et al., 2025) and—when applied to short-term rentals—to mitigate housing-market pressures by moderating competition for residential stock (Nieuwland & Van Melik, 2020; Von Briel & Dolnicar, 2020). Complementing these fiscal measures, spatial and urban planning strategies can help steer visitor flows and redistribute tourism intensity across space, easing tourism intensity while preserving destination-wide economic benefits (Shoval, 2018; Yuval, 2022). Alongside fiscal instruments and spatial and urban planning strategies, environmental regulation represents an additional policy lever through which destinations can address tourism-related externalities. It can

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encourage tourism organizations to adopt more responsible practices toward the destination and, in the specific case of eco-taxes, contribute to the internalization and compensation of environmental damages associated with tourism activity (Do Valle et al., 2012; Rossello-Nadal & Sard, 2026).

Despite the growing deployment of regulatory instruments, empirical evidence on their effectiveness remains limited and is often fragmented across single policy domains such as environmental regulation, spatial planning, or taxation. Florence, one of Europe's most visited cities, has faced sustained tourism pressure over the past decade, with observable repercussions for its urban fabric, local economy, and residents' quality of life (Kramer, 2023; Statista Research Department, 2024). Against this backdrop, this study examines the effectiveness of regulatory interventions in managing tourism intensity. We employ a mixed-methods research design to assess whether the regulatory approach adopted by Florence's destination managers has been effective in governing tourism intensity. First, we conduct a content analysis of municipal regulations to identify policy interventions that directly target the tourism sector as well as those that may affect it indirectly. Based on this coding, we construct a measure of tourism regulatory pressure to assess whether policymakers resort to regulation as a tool to manage tourism intensity. Our results show that policymakers increased the level of regulatory pressure over the period 2015–2022, and that, during phases of heightened risk associated with unsustainable levels of tourism, tourism-oriented regulations emerged as the primary policy instrument. Second, we estimate an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression model to test whether regulatory pressure is statistically associated with tourism intensity. Because the analysis relies on monthly time-series data, we report Newey–West (HAC) standard errors and include monthly seasonality controls to ensure conservative inference under autocorrelation and heteroskedasticity. The qualitative analysis provides contextual grounding, while the quantitative results assess the relationship's robustness (Hsu, 2024).

The results document a negative and statistically significant association between regulatory pressure and tourism intensity, suggesting that regulatory interventions can play an effective role in reducing tourism intensity and advancing more sustainable destination management. Crucially, policy interventions that affect the tourism sector—both directly and indirectly—are associated with lower visitor pressure, and measures that directly target tourism exhibit a stronger effect. In addition to these critical insights, the study advances a methodological contribution by operationalizing regulatory pressure in a way that reflects heterogeneity across policy instruments. By incorporating variation in instrument type, scope, and enforceability, our approach offers a more fine-grained characterization of the regulatory environment and provides a transferable framework for assessing regulatory mixes across destinations. Taken together, the findings point to a destination-management strategy that prioritizes tourism-specific regulation as a comparatively more effective lever for governing tourism intensity.

2. Schematic overview, data, and method

2.1. Framework and hypothesis

In destinations where tourism intensity is a primary concern, policymakers have increasingly relied on urban-planning and zoning measures to manage tourism-related land uses. Amsterdam, for instance, addressed overcrowding by restricting or closing bars, coffeehouses, and entertainment venues in particularly congested areas (Yuval, 2022). While such interventions can redistribute visitor activity spatially, they often leave aggregate tourism pressure largely unchanged by displacing demand rather than reducing it.

Beyond land-use regulation, policymakers have also targeted tourism's spillovers into housing markets. Barcelona, Paris, and London, among others, have tightened rules on short-term rentals to mitigate adverse effects on affordability and residential livability (Bei & Celata,

2023; Kirilenko et al., 2023; Von Briel & Dolnicar, 2020). These measures aim to protect the social sustainability of central neighborhoods and the integrity of heritage settings, yet they may also generate unintended consequences for conventional accommodation supply and reallocate pressures across adjacent residential areas (Bei & Celata, 2023; Von Briel & Dolnicar, 2020). Although such regulation is intended to support residents and improve quality of life, it may also face political and industry resistance, underscoring the contested nature of tourism governance (Randle & Hoye, 2016).

A more direct policy approach seeks to influence tourism intensity by limiting, rationing, or pricing access to sensitive areas (Han et al., 2021; Mihalic, 2020). Venice introduced a mandatory access fee for entry to the historic center with the stated aim of safeguarding a fragile urban and environmental equilibrium. However, emerging evidence suggests that pricing access alone is unlikely to generate sustained reductions in congestion, thereby reinforcing calls for more integrated and coordinated policy mixes (Città di Venezia, 2024).

More in general, destination managers have responded to escalating tourism pressure through an increasingly regulatory toolkit (Tokarchuk et al., 2021). Yet the persistence of overcrowding indicates that measures implemented in a fragmented manner and with limited coordination can weaken overall policy effectiveness in shaping visitor flows and spatial concentrations (Becken et al., 2020). Because tourism regulation operates through multiple channels and is designed and implemented as an integrated set of measures within a single governance context, we examine the combined regulatory environment rather than attempting to attribute changes in tourism intensity to individual acts in isolation. Therefore, if regulation is an effective tool used by destination managers to control tourism intensity, the following relationship should be expected:

H1. *Regulatory pressure is negatively associated with the intensity of tourism.*

This framework is reported Fig. 1 and summarizes the relationship between regulatory pressure and tourism intensity.

2.2. Case study: the regulatory pressure in Florence

The theoretical framework is applied to the city of Florence, which counts among the world's most visited cultural sites and has been defined as one of the most “touristified metropolitan cities” in Italy (Celata & Romano, 2020, p. 2; Scarpi et al., 2022). As early as the 17th and 18th centuries, the city drew young European aristocrats undertaking the Grand Tour, thus playing a significant role in the emergence of urban tourism in Europe (Kramer, 2023) and today it continues to hold a prominent place in international tourism rankings (Francini, 2023). Florence's historic center spans 5.3 km² and received more than 2 million tourist arrivals in 2023, almost reaching 3 million pre-COVID-19 pandemic levels (Statista Research Department, 2024). However, the dense concentration of cultural assets has led to negative consequences as inflated housing and dining prices, loss of residential services, and a marked population decline, especially in the historic center (Scarpi et al., 2022; Statista Research Department, 2024).

Concerns over tourism levels have become so serious that UNESCO considered revoking Florence's World Heritage status due to delays in implementing preservation measures outlined in 2006 in the city's first Management Plan (Francini, 2023). In subsequent updates, the city's Management Plan explicitly identifies excessive tourism pressure as a key threat and promotes regulatory measures to protect its “*outstanding universal value*” (Francini, 2023). Therefore, regulatory measures issued

Fig. 1. Framework for the relation between regulatory pressure and tourism. Source: Authors' design.

by the Municipality of Florence and UNESCO's Florence office¹ have been strengthened to answer specific tourism management needs and mitigate its negative externalities (UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 2012; Liu et al., 2020). Interventions include, for example, regulatory and fiscal measures on short-term rentals, quantitative limitations on tourism activities, behavioural regulations, spatial and collaboration strategies. Appendix A draws a picture of the main regulatory actions and their expected outcomes.

Finally, tourism governance has been strengthened through the developments of sustainability indicators embedded in the city's management plan to monitor tourism dynamics. These tools enable evidence-based evaluation of regulatory effectiveness and help managing tourism pressure through targeted and adaptive regulation (UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 2012).

2.3. Methodology and data

To examine the relationship between regulatory pressure and tourism intensity we used a mixed-method approach combining content analysis with regression analysis. The multimethod approach was selected for its effectiveness in addressing interdisciplinary questions and tracking policy changes, also offering an in-depth understanding of the results (Hsu, 2024; Ivars-Baidal et al., 2023). Fig. 2 outlines the methodology.

Data sources include:

- Regulations: Municipality of Florence and UNESCO Florence office.
- Tourism and socioeconomic data: Florence Statistical Office and UNESCO.

2.3.1. Content analysis

We manually reviewed 248 municipal regulatory documents enacted from 2015 to 2022, retaining 85 that were tourism related. A document was included if its objectives or measures explicitly addressed tourism (based on the principle; Becken et al., 2020). Each regulation was

classified as “in force” or “expired” according to its enforcement period (Becken et al., 2020).

To ensure consistency, all researchers reviewed independently and compared the categorization to reach consensus, when necessary. The key criterion that guided the content analysis was materiality (Becken et al., 2020), determined by manually verifying whether the document's objectives, action points, or measures addressed tourism. If a regulation met this criterion, we classified it as a “tourism regulation;” otherwise, the regulation was excluded from the analysis. Regulatory pressure was measured as the monthly proportion of active tourism-related regulations relative to the total number of regulatory documents. We excluded those no longer in force.

2.3.2. Regression analysis

We estimate a set of linear regression models to test whether higher regulatory pressure is associated with lower tourism intensity, using the following econometric specification. Coefficients are obtained via OLS, while standard errors are computed using Newey–West (HAC) corrections to ensure conservative inference in the presence of serial correlation and heteroskedasticity typical of monthly time-series data. We also include month fixed effects to absorb recurrent seasonal patterns in tourism demand and related covariates, thereby improving robustness to seasonality-driven fluctuations in the monthly time series. We adopt the following econometric model:

$$\text{Tourism_Intensity}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Reg_Pressure}_{t-1} + \beta_2 \text{Growth}_t + \beta_3 \text{Inflation}_t + \beta_4 \text{GDP}_t + \beta_5 \text{Tourist_Tax}_t + \beta_6 \text{Housing_Prices}_t + \beta_7 \text{Hospitality_Rate}_t + \text{Month fixed effects} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

where *Tourism_Intensity* is the dependent variable that captures the intensity of tourism. As the number of visitors is a widely used indicator in tourism analysis (Marinello et al., 2023; Song & Li, 2008), *Tourism_Intensity* was measured as the number of monthly arrivals divided by the city's square meters. Further, the existing literature provides evidence that tourism intensity negatively affects residents' welfare and daily lives (Tokarchuk et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2022). As a robustness check, we redefined tourism intensity using the surface area of Florence's city center as the spatial denominator. Our key independent variable, *Regulatory Pressure*, captures the regulatory pressure in Florence and is measured as illustrated in the previous section. To reduce structural dependence, the variable is lagged by one and two months, as past outcomes might influence economic variables (Wooldridge et al., 2016).

¹ This office is part of the administrative structure of the Municipality of Florence and is responsible for complying with the UNESCO provisions, acting as an intermediary between the World Heritage Center in Paris and the Municipality of Florence.

Fig. 2. Phases of the designed methodology. Source: Authors' design.

Control variables, all measured monthly, include gross domestic product (GDP), inflation, tourism tax, arrival growth rate, housing rate, housing prices, and hospitality occupancy. Following Ridderstaat et al. (2022), we transformed housing and hospitality variables into logarithms to correct for heteroskedasticity or skewness concerns in the data (Wooldridge et al., 2016). All variables were winsorized at the 1st and 99th percentiles to reduce outlier bias (Wooldridge et al., 2016). Appendix B provides detailed variable definitions and measurement information.

3. Findings and discussion

3.1. Analysis of regulatory pressure and tourism intensity

To comply with UNESCO's requirements and avoid losing the World Heritage status, in 2015 policymakers issued numerous regulations addressing the growing unsustainability of tourism. While intervention levels declined between 2016 and 2019, the number of regulations rose again from 2020 to 2022. The increase addressed public health and safety during the COVID-19 pandemic, while post-pandemic measures

Table 1
Main analyses: the association between tourism intensity and regulatory pressure in Florence.

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Tourism_Intensity	Tourism_Intensity	Tourism_Intensity2	Tourism_Intensity2
<i>Reg_Pressure_{t-1}</i>	-0.003*** (0.001)		-0.244*** (0.074)	
<i>Reg_Pressure_{t-2}</i>		-0.003*** (0.001)		-0.230*** (0.073)
<i>Growth</i>	-0.056 (0.045)	-0.067 (0.043)	-4.220 (3.395)	-4.993 (3.243)
<i>Inflation</i>	0.143*** (0.036)	0.137*** (0.037)	10.779*** (2.725)	10.395*** (2.765)
<i>GDP</i>	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.117 (0.140)	-0.129 (0.148)
<i>Tourist_Tax</i>	0.061 (0.053)	0.065 (0.057)	4.561 (3.963)	4.804 (4.275)
<i>Housing_Prices</i>	-0.735 (3.293)	-1.164 (3.332)	-57.987 (250.163)	-88.939 (252.986)
<i>Hospitality_Rate</i>	3.019** (1.241)	2.907** (1.274)	224.540** (94.173)	215.886** (96.583)
<i>Constant</i>	-0.016 (0.026)	-0.012 (0.026)	-1.175 (1.992)	-0.869 (1.955)
<i>Month f.e.</i>	YES	YES	YES	YES
N. obs.	95	94	95	94
F-statistics	6.039***	6.828***	6.271***	7.063***

Robust standard errors in parentheses ****p* < 0.01, ***p* < 0.05, **p* < 0.10.

sought to manage tourism's rapid recovery. In the period of analysis, an average of ten regulations per year were enacted, progressively increasing overall regulatory pressure. Appendix C – Panel A reports the annual distribution of tourism-related regulations.

The main effect analysis is presented in Columns (1)–(4) of Table 1. Overall, the results demonstrate the significance of the model based on the F-statistics ($p < 0.01$) in all the columns. Additionally, the variance inflation factor (VIF) was also calculated and showed no multicollinearity concerns among the independent variables, ensuring the reliability of the OLS estimates. Across all specifications, the estimated coefficient on regulatory pressure is negative and statistically significant, indicating that higher regulatory pressure is followed by lower tourism density.

Columns (1) and (2) use the baseline measure of tourism intensity (*Tourism_Intensity*). *Regulatory pressure* displays a negative and strongly significant association when lagged by one month ($p < 0.01$; Column 1) and remains negative and significant when lagged by two months ($p < 0.01$; Column 2). These results suggest that months following a higher level of tourism-related regulatory activity—captured by our content index of active municipal acts—are associated with lower visitor density, conditional on macroeconomic conditions and other controls. Indeed, municipal interventions may require time to be implemented and reflected in market outcomes, with effects materializing in subsequent months rather than contemporaneously. The small reduction in the number of observations in the $t-2$ specification reflects the additional lag structure.

Columns (3) and (4) replicate the analysis using an alternative operationalization of tourism intensity (*Tourism_Intensity2*) as a robustness check. The coefficient on regulatory pressure remains negative and statistically significant for both lag structures ($p < 0.01$; Column 3 and Column 4). While the magnitude of the coefficients differs mechanically because the dependent variables are measured on different scales, the sign, statistical significance, and overall inference are fully consistent with Columns (1)–(2), reinforcing the robustness of the main finding across alternative definitions of tourism intensity.

Regarding the control variables, the results are stable across specifications. Inflation is positive and statistically significant in all models ($p < 0.01$), and the hospitality rate (occupancy) is also positive and significant, consistent with higher accommodation occupancy being associated with greater visitor pressure. By contrast, the coefficients for the tourism tax are not statistically significant in any model specifications, suggesting that variations in the city tax do not affect the intensity of tourism flows. Furthermore, when translated into realistic distribution-based shifts (e.g., one standard deviation or an interquartile-range increase in regulatory pressure), the estimated coefficients imply significant reductions in tourism intensity relative to both the outcome's mean and its typical month-to-month variability, supporting the substantive relevance of the finding.

In untabulated results, we further benchmark the magnitude of the regulatory-pressure effect against the empirical distribution and short-run dynamics of *Tourism_Intensity*. Specifically, we translate the estimated coefficient into distribution-consistent changes in *Reg_Pressure* (one standard deviation and an interquartile-range shift) and compare the implied changes with both the mean/standard deviation of *Tourism_Intensity* and its typical month-to-month variation. The results show that realistic increases in regulatory pressure correspond to sizeable reductions in tourism intensity, reinforcing the substantive relevance of the main finding.

3.2. Tourism-centered vs tourism-related regulations

To further investigate our main results, we conducted an additional manual content analysis to explore the type of regulatory pressure in Florence and differentiate the regulations on the basis of their focus. We classify a regulation as *tourism-centered* if it specifically refers to tourism as the key management area. Otherwise, we define a regulation as

tourism-related if it includes tourism but does not emphasize it as a primary area of concern. This classification, illustrated in Fig. 3, enables a more nuanced understanding of efficacy.

We measured tourism-centered (tourism-related) regulatory pressure for a given month as the proportion of tourism-centered (tourism-related) regulations related to the total number of regulatory documents. Appendix C – Panel B reports the results of the contents analysis showing that tourism-centered regulations outnumber tourism-related regulations, thereby exerting greater regulatory pressure.

In the early years of the analysis (2015–2019), this difference was not significant, as tourism-centered regulations constituted 60 % of the total regulatory interventions. However, in subsequent years, the incidence increased significantly to 80 %. This may be due to the rapid rebound of tourism in 2022. In fact, since the pandemic period was not used to implement long-term measures to develop sustainable tourism, the Municipality reacted in 2022 with 11 tourism-centered interventions to anticipate the risk of excessive tourism recovery.

We then re-estimated the regression models (1) using two distinct proxies for the regulatory pressure variable: *Centered_Reg_Pressure*, which captures regulations explicitly aimed at the tourism sector, and *Related_Reg_Pressure*, which reflects non-tourism-specific regulations that may still influence tourism indirectly. The results of these regressions are reported in Table 2.

Columns (1)–(2) report the effects of *Centered_Reg_Pressure*. The coefficients are negative and statistically significant at the 1 % level for both the one-month and two-month lags, indicating that increases in tourism-targeted regulatory activity are systematically followed by lower *Tourism_Intensity* in subsequent months. Our results support the interpretation that sector-specific municipal interventions can operate as an effective mechanism for moderating visitor pressure, with effects materializing within a one–two month horizon.

Columns (3) and (4) present the results for the association between tourism-related regulations and tourism intensity by one- and two-month lags, respectively. Comparing Columns (1)–(2) with Columns (3)–(4) suggests that the strongest and most consistent reductions in tourism intensity are associated with measures that explicitly target the tourism sector, while broader regulatory actions also matter but operate as a secondary channel.

The control variables behave consistently across all models. *Inflation* and *Hospitality rate* show a positive and significant association with tourism intensity ($p < 0.01$) in every specification, while tourist tax and economic growth (*GDP* and *Growth*) show no statistical significance. To test our results' robustness, we run the same set of regressions employing *Tourism_Intensity2* as the dependent variable and find consistent evidence regarding the sign and economic magnitude of those reported in Table 2 (untabulated results). Taken together, Table 2 indicates that both tourism-specific and tourism-adjacent regulations are followed by reductions in visitor density, with the clearest and most robust associations arising for explicitly tourism-centered measures.

These results strengthen the evidence provided in Table 1 and are consistent with UNESCO's recommendations on sustainable tourism governance. Specifically, these findings provide evidence that regulations directly addressing tourism are more effective in reducing tourism intensity than non-tourism-specific regulations. Overall, the findings highlight the strategic role of local policymakers and destination managers in promoting sustainable tourism through sector-specific regulatory interventions, particularly in cities suffering from intense tourism flows, such as Florence.

4. Discussion and conclusions

4.1. Discussion

This study empirically investigates the impact of regulatory pressure on tourism intensity using a mixed-methods approach. Through manual content analysis, we assessed the local regulatory framework and

Fig. 3. Framework for the relation between tourism-centered and tourism-related regulatory pressure and tourism intensity. Source: Authors' design.

Table 2

Additional analyses: the association between tourism-centered and tourism-related regulatory pressure and tourism intensity in Florence.

Variables	(1) Tourism_Intensity	(2) Tourism_Intensity	(3) Tourism_Intensity	(4) Tourism_Intensity
<i>Centered_Reg_Pressure_{t-1}</i>	-0.006*** (0.002)			
<i>Centered_Reg_Pressure_{t-2}</i>		-0.005*** (0.002)		
<i>Related_Reg_Pressure_{t-1}</i>			-0.005** (0.002)	
<i>Related_Reg_Pressure_{t-2}</i>				-0.005*** (0.002)
<i>Growth</i>	-0.039 (0.044)	-0.058 (0.041)	-0.093* (0.049)	-0.091* (0.048)
<i>Inflation</i>	0.164*** (0.040)	0.150*** (0.041)	0.097*** (0.033)	0.103*** (0.031)
<i>GDP</i>	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)
<i>Tourist_Tax</i>	0.045 (0.055)	0.060 (0.060)	0.110* (0.056)	0.098* (0.059)
<i>Housing_Prices</i>	0.989 (3.330)	-0.021 (3.460)	-4.255 (3.155)	-3.974 (3.254)
<i>Hospitality_Rate</i>	2.850** (1.139)	2.711** (1.220)	3.063** (1.400)	3.049** (1.379)
<i>Constant</i>	-0.029 (0.027)	-0.020 (0.027)	0.010 (0.024)	0.009 (0.024)
<i>Month f.e.</i>	YES	YES	YES	YES
N. obs.	95	94	95	94
F-statistics	6.154***	7.471***	10.750***	10.450***

Robust standard errors in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.10$.

quantified regulatory pressure. The findings, based on the case of Florence, Italy, highlight that the city implemented a wave of tourism regulations in 2015 to align with UNESCO World Heritage Site standards, followed by a second phase of regulations during the post-COVID-19 recovery. Within the overall increase in regulatory pressure, our results also indicate that policymakers relied more heavily on tourism-centered interventions during periods in which the risk of excessive tourism intensity was perceived to be higher. Then, regression models were performed to examine the relationship with tourism intensity. Our results reveal a negative association between regulatory pressure and tourism intensity. This relationship is especially pronounced for tourism-specific regulations, which had a growing impact over time. In contrast, general regulations—such as those addressing housing or urban space—had only a marginal effect on tourism intensity.

Our study advances the literature on managing overtourism (e.g., Mihalic, 2020), by offering a new methodology to evaluate policy effectiveness. While existing research has predominantly focused on diagnosing overtourism through indicators of crowding or sustainability (e.g. Marinello et al., 2023), or on the effect of specific regulations (e.g. Bei & Celata, 2023), comparatively limited effort has been devoted to systematically assessing whether and how integrated regulatory responses alter tourism dynamics. By operationalizing regulatory pressure through content analysis of policy instruments, this study captures not only the presence but also the scope and heterogeneity of policy instruments. Thus, we contribute introducing a replicable methodological approach that can be applied across urban destinations allowing comparisons between different regulatory domains. In doing so, it complements studies relying on interviews (e.g., Haigh, 2020) and qualitative

policy analyses (e.g., York & Zhang, 2010), strengthening the empirical toolkit available for comparative destination management research.

4.2. Policy implications

The study provides quantitative evidence that policy interventions can exert a measurable change in tourism dynamics. The Florence case suggests that targeted, tourism-centered regulations, such as short-term rental rules, visitor thresholds, and timed-entry systems, are more effective than broad tourism-related interventions. This implies that policymakers should prioritize sector-specific design when crafting regulations, focusing on critical pressure points within the destination system (e.g. excessive levels of tourists, housing affordability issues, etc.). Practically, this approach suggests policymakers and local authorities to intervene selectively on tourism's negative externalities through tourism-centered regulatory interventions. As such, targeted regulation emerges as a transferable strategy for policymakers of other urban destinations seeking to balance tourism demand with heritage protection and residents' quality of life. Similar instruments could be promoted by policymakers across different urban contexts, such as mandatory tourist codes of conduct, priority public transport access for residents during peak hours (as implemented in Venice), or fiscal incentives for long-term rentals illustrate. These tools help reconcile tourism demand with cultural heritage protection and residents' quality of life (Rossello-Nadal & Sard, 2026; Wang et al., 2022).

Additionally, policymakers should avoid regulatory proliferation. Our evidence suggests that better results (intended as a reduction in tourism intensity) emerge from fewer but tourism-specific regulations, combined with monitoring systems that support adaptive governance. This implies that tourism regulation should be conceived by policymakers as an iterative process that can be adjusted as conditions evolve, rather than as a fixed, one-time policy response.

Finally, evidence from Florence suggests that policymakers should invest in institutional capacity-building since regulatory effectiveness depends on the capacity of local institutions to monitor tourism dynamics, coordinate policy domains, and adjust interventions over time, in line with adaptive governance frameworks (e.g. Mancini et al., 2020; Nieuwland et al., 2025). This also implies that policymakers and destination managers should embed sustainability indicators into destination management frameworks to enable systematic feedback between observed outcomes and policy revisions, allowing to refine interventions over time and enhance their effectiveness.

4.3. Limitations

This study is not without limitations. A potential caveat lies in the generalizability of our findings to other urban contexts. Florence's historic center is an urban environment shaped by a strong historical identity and strict conservation policies due to its UNESCO World Heritage status. Accordingly, our findings offer valuable insights for other urban destinations facing similar challenges (Francini, 2023; Mihalic, 2020), while cities experiencing tourism pressure without such designation may face different regulatory and socio-economic dynamics. Further comparative research across diverse urban contexts could be conducted replicating the quali-quantitative methodology designed in

this research. Nonetheless, the regulatory pressure index developed in this study could be adapted by policymakers and researchers to simulate the potential impact of new regulations and guide decision-making. Additionally, future research could apply alternative methodologies, such as automated textual analysis of local documents, across a wider range of destinations, and extend the temporal extent by examining a broader time span, thus allowing for more comprehensive longitudinal and spatial comparisons. Such efforts would strengthen the understanding of how regulation can be used as a proactive tool in sustainable tourism governance.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Rebecca Miccini: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Camilla Ciappei:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Giovanni Liberatore:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Impact statement

Tourism at World Heritage Sites has surged in recent years, intensifying challenges related to overtourism, environmental degradation, and reduced livability. While existing studies often quantify tourism flows, few evaluate the effectiveness of regulatory responses. This study addresses that gap by examining Florence, Italy—a UNESCO World Heritage Site experiencing significant tourism pressure. Using a mixed-method approach that combines manual content analysis and OLS regression, we assess how regulatory actions by local authorities influence tourism intensity. Our findings demonstrate that increased regulatory pressure is associated with reduced tourism intensity, highlighting the value of proactive governance. These results offer practical implications for destination managers and policymakers seeking to design evidence-based regulations that balance tourism growth with cultural heritage preservation and local well-being.

Declaration of ompeting interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Appendix A

Regulatory actions and expected outcomes for the city of Florence.

Scope of regulation	Regulatory instrument	Examples (non-exhaustive)	Expected outcomes
<i>Tourism-centered</i>	Short-term rental regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mandatory registration of short-term rentals; - Application of a tourist tax to short-term rentals; - Suspension of the authorization of new short-term rental apartments in the historic center; - Bans of outdoor key boxes affixed on heritage buildings. 	Increased compliance costs for short-term rental operators, enhancement of market transparency, and reducing pressure on housing availability, (Nieuwland & Van Melik, 2020; Von Briel & Dolnicar, 2020).
	Restrictions on tourism-related activities and behavioural norms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction of timed entry tickets for major attractions; - Restrictions on tour group sizes; - Behavioural restriction as forbidding to eat street food on sacred monuments. 	Reduced congestion at iconic sites, improved urban liveability, and preservation of economic and residential diversity. (Scarpi et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022)
<i>Tourism-related</i>	Planning and zoning initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of alternative itineraries; - Collaboration with nearby cities. 	Support the redistribution of tourism pressure (Shoval, 2018; Yuval, 2022).
	Management of public areas and urban planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulation on inbound traffic; - Occupation of public soil; - Urban planning regulations. 	Definition of how public space and urban areas can be used and accessed to ensure safe and efficient circulation, and government of the occupation of public land.
	Management of commercial activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulation of commerce on public soil; - Preservation of historic commercial activities; - Limits to the opening of new food businesses in the city center. 	Set rules for conducting business, preserve local identity, and impose limits on new licenses in the city center to maintain urban balance.
	Protection of cultural and human heritage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Management plan for the city; - Regulations to protect healthiness and quality of life. 	Establish strategic guidelines for how the city is managed, ensure that development and daily activities do not compromise public health or overall quality of life, and maintain a liveable urban environment.

Appendix B

Variables definition.

Variable	Description	Source
<i>Tourism_Intensity</i>	Number of tourism arrivals in Florence divided by the number of residents	Accommodation Facilities and Tourism Statistics Office of the Metropolitan City of Florence
<i>Tourism_Intensity₂</i>	Number of monthly arrivals in Florence divided by the city's square meters	Accommodation Facilities and Tourism Statistics Office of the Metropolitan City of Florence ^b
<i>Reg_Pressure</i>	The monthly proportion of active tourism-related regulations relative to the total number of regulatory documents (Florence). The variable is lagged by one and two months, as past outcomes might influence economic variables	Content analysis as discussed in the previous paragraph
<i>Growth</i>	Arrival's monthly growth rate (Florence)	Calculated by the authors on the basis of data provided for the tourism intensity variable
<i>Inflation</i>	Monthly Florence's inflation rate	Accommodation Facilities and Tourism Statistics Office of the Metropolitan City of Florence
<i>GDP</i>	Monthly gdp for the city of Florence	Accommodation Facilities and Tourism Statistics Office of the Metropolitan City of Florence
<i>Tourist_Tax</i>	Monthly tourist (accommodation) tax revenue in Florence	Accommodation Facilities and Tourism Statistics Office of the Metropolitan City of Florence
<i>Housing_Prices</i>	Average monthly listing price (€/sqm) of residential properties for sale in Florence ^a	Idealista https://www.idealista.it/sala-stampa/report-prezzo-immobile/vendita/toscana/firenze-provincia/firenze/
<i>Hospitality_Rate</i>	Monthly occupancy rate of accommodation establishments (overnight stays/number of beds) ^a	Accommodation Facilities and Tourism Statistics Office of the Metropolitan City of Florence

Nb. All variables were winsorized at the 1st and 99th percentiles to reduce outlier bias (Wooldridge et al., 2016).

^a Calculated as logarithms to correct for heteroskedasticity or skewness concerns in the data (Wooldridge et al., 2016).

^b Ufficio Strutture ricettive e statistiche del turismo della Città Metropolitana di Firenze.

Appendix C

Panel A – Annual distribution of tourism-related regulations in Florence.

Year	Number of regulations	Cumulative frequency
2015	21	21
2016	6	27
2017	2	29

(continued on next page)

Appendix C (continued)

Year	Number of regulations	Cumulative frequency
2018	10	39
2019	5	44
2020	11	55
2021	18	73
2022	12	85
Total	85	85

Appendix C

Panel B – Distribution of tourism-centered and tourism-related regulations.

Year	Tourism-centered regulations	Tourism-related regulations	Total regulations
2015	10	11	21
2016	4	2	6
2017	2	0	2
2018	7	3	10
2019	2	3	5
2020	9	2	11
2021	12	6	18
2022	11	1	12
Total	57	28	85

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